

Notes

Metal-Ligand Stability Constants of Heterocyclic Hydroxamic Acids

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For the application of hydroxamic acids in analytical chemistry it is desirable to have a knowledge of the stabilities of their chelates with various metal ions. In the present investigation thermodynamic stability constants of the complexes formed by Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II} and Ba^{II} with heterocyclic hydroxamic acids, have been determined by pH-titration method in 70% dioxan-water media at 25°. The details of the method and experimental procedure are essentially the same as described elsewhere^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic metal-ligand stability constants have been determined in 70% dioxan-water since the complexes were not soluble in lower dioxan concentration. The values of stability constants are given in Table 1.

It has been shown by several workers^{2,5} that the plots of pK_a of substituted ligand against the log *k*₁ (or log *k*₂ or log *k*₁*k*₂) of the particular metal ion exist a linear relationship. A similar relationship is observed when the stability constants of Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II} and Ba^{II} are plotted against pK_a of substituted heterocyclic hydroxamic acids showing that a linear relation for log *K*₁ and pK_a, is obtained. The log *K*₁ and log *K*₂ values (Table 1) for the metal complexes examined here show the following order, irrespective of the substituents in hydroxamic acid: Be^{II} > Mg^{II} > Ca^{II} > Ba^{II}. The same order of stabilities

of these metal chelates have been reported with other ligand, viz. aminobarbituric acid, *N,N*-diacetic acid etc.⁶.

In the present study, all the alkali earth metal ions are in the +2 oxidation state so the electrostatic contribution to metal-ligand bond in the first complexes formed with the same ligand is assumed to be almost the same. Irving and Williams showed that the plots of log *K*₁ of the complexes versus the overall ionisation potential of divalent metals gives a straight line⁷; the same trend is observed with alkali earth ions Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II} and Ba^{II}. Similarly a linear relationship is observed between the stability constant of alkali metals and heterocyclic hydroxamate complexes with charge/radius and reciprocal of the ionic radii of metal ions. Table 1 shows that for all the systems studied here log *K*₁ - log *K*₂ is positive and lies within 1 to 1.3 log units.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merck) grade.

The hydroxamic acids were synthesised as described elsewhere³. Generally these acids were synthesised by reacting acid chlorides with hydroxylamine in equimolar proportions in presence of ether and aqueous suspension of sodium bicarbonate.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF HETEROCYCLIC HYDROXAMIC ACIDS IN 70% (v/v) DIOXAN-WATER

Ion	Stability constant	Phenyl-2-furo-	<i>p</i> -Tolyl-2-furo-	<i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl-2-furo-	<i>m</i> -Cl-Phenyl-2-furo-	Phenyl-2-theno-	<i>p</i> -Tolyl-2-theno-	<i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl-2-theno-	<i>m</i> -Cl-Phenyl-2-theno-
H ⁺	pK _a	12.53	12.81	12.70	12.60	12.60	12.92	12.75	12.68
Be ²⁺	log <i>K</i> ₁	9.98	10.40	10.25	10.00	10.11	10.62	10.40	10.20
	log <i>K</i> ₂	8.72	9.20	9.00	8.36	8.90	9.40	9.21	8.97
Mg ²⁺	log <i>K</i> ₁	7.00	7.80	7.46	7.18	7.27	8.02	7.64	7.34
	log <i>K</i> ₂	5.87	6.62	6.34	6.03	6.16	6.86	6.44	6.20
Ca ²⁺	log <i>K</i> ₁	6.70	7.40	7.10	6.84	6.92	7.62	7.25	7.02
	log <i>K</i> ₂	5.54	6.20	5.89	5.68	5.77	6.46	6.05	5.87
Ba ²⁺	log <i>K</i> ₁	6.46	7.12	6.86	6.60	6.70	7.36	7.0	6.80
	log <i>K</i> ₂	5.26	5.94	5.66	5.40	5.52	6.18	5.82	5.64

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Procedure · To hydroxamic acid (corresponding to 0.01 M solution in a final volume of 50 ml) was added freshly distilled dioxan (35 ml) followed by the metal solution (5 ml) and water (10 ml). Due allowance for the contraction in volume of mixing of the two solvents was made⁴. Then the mixture was thermostated at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and nitrogen presaturated with 70% dioxan-water mixture was bubbled through the solution. The solution was titrated with 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium hydroxide adding the same in small aliquots and noting the pH-meter reading (*B*) each time, using glass and calomel electrodes.

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